

Comparative Analysis of SAW Substrate Materials for Unit Resonators

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Abstract— This paper provides an in-depth comparative analysis of different substrate materials for unit resonators in Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW) technology, including Quartz (SiO₂), Lithium Niobate (LiNbO₃), Lithium Tantalate (LiTaO₃), Zinc Oxide (ZnO), Gallium Arsenide (GaAs), Aluminum Nitride (AlN), Lanthanum Gallium Silicate (Langasite, La₃Ga₅SiO₁₄), Potassium Niobate (KNbO₃), Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT), and Gallium Nitride (GaN). The assessment of these substances considered important factors like their Voigt notation elasticity matrix, piezoelectric coupling matrix, relative permittivity, and density. The suitability for high-efficiency SAW resonators of each substrate was systematically investigated using Rayleigh waves, electric field plots, and resonant frequency measurements. Our results emphasize the pros and cons of each material's mechanical and electrical properties, offering important guidance for choosing the best substrates in SAW device use. This study intends to assist researchers and engineers in making well-informed decisions while designing SAW resonators for different technological uses.

Keywords— Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW), Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS), Carrier Aggregation (CA), Transmitter Front End (TxFE), wireless communication, signal interference, spectral efficiency, RF front-end modules.

I. INTRODUCTION

SAW technology has a significant impact on various contemporary uses like signal processing, sensors, and resonators. The performance of Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW) devices is significantly influenced by the substrate materials utilized, as these materials impact the transmission of acoustic waves due to their specific physical characteristics. This paper compares ten major SAW substrate materials: Quartz (SiO₂), Lithium Niobate (LiNbO₃), Lithium Tantalate (LiTaO₃), Zinc Oxide (ZnO), Gallium Arsenide (GaAs), Aluminum Nitride (AlN), Lanthanum Gallium Silicate (Langasite, La₃Ga₅SiO₁₄), Potassium Niobate (KNbO₃), Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT), and Gallium Nitride (GaN).

We assess these substances by considering their major characteristics, such as elasticity matrix in Voigt notation, piezoelectric coupling matrix, relative permittivity, and density. These factors are essential as they determine the speed of the wave, effectiveness, and overall functionality of SAW gadgets. In our examination, we make use of Rayleigh waves, which travel on the surface of the material with distinctive elliptical particle movement and absence of traction at the boundaries. Rayleigh wave velocity is greatly influenced by the material of the substrate and its crystal orientation, as stated in the equation provided.

$$dV = (\partial V / \partial m \, dm + \partial V / \partial E \, dE + \partial V / \partial M_i \, dM_i + \partial V / \partial \epsilon_v \, d\epsilon_v)$$

We also explore how various physical and environmental factors affect the acoustic wave velocity (V) in the substrates. Using the chain rule, we express the change in wave velocity (∂V) as influenced by mass (m), electrical properties (E), mechanical properties (M_i), and environmental factors (ϵ_v):

$$cR = cS(0.87 + 1.12\nu/1+\nu)$$

This holistic method enables us to methodically assess the materials, emphasizing their advantages and drawbacks for SAW resonator usage. In this research, we provide in-depth electric field diagrams and measurements of resonant frequencies for every material. These assessments offer important

understanding on the appropriateness of each substrate for high-performance SAW resonators, helping researchers and engineers choose the best material for their particular needs. Our goal is to further SAW technology advancement by evaluating the performance of these ten materials, which can drive innovation in telecommunications, medical diagnostics, and environmental monitoring. Our results highlight the significance of selecting materials for designing and optimizing SAW devices, potentially leading to improved technologies in the future.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Choosing the right substrate material is crucial in enhancing the efficiency of SAW resonators. Nevertheless, there remains a deficiency in thorough comparative research that assesses these materials using uniform standards. The existence of this gap poses a challenge for researchers and engineers in choosing the best substrate material for particular applications. The main goal of this research is to conduct a structured comparison of the mentioned SAW substrate materials. Rayleigh waves, electric field plots, and resonant frequency measurements will be utilized in this analysis. The evaluation of the materials will be done considering their mechanical and electrical characteristics, which include their elasticity matrix, piezoelectric coupling matrix, relative permittivity, and density.

III. METHODOLOGY

Step 1. Characteristic Parameters of SAW Resonators

Resonant Frequency (f_s): Frequency at which the series LC circuit in the mBVD model resonates.

Anti-Resonant Frequency (f_p): Frequency influenced by the coupling between the capacitors in the mBVD model.

Electromechanical Coupling Coefficient (k_t^2): Indicates the efficiency of energy conversion between electrical and mechanical forms, calculated by $k_t^2 = 1 - [(f_s/f_p)]^2$.

Quality Factors (Q_s and Q_p): Measure the losses at resonant and anti-resonant frequencies, respectively.

$$Z_{in} = 1/s \cdot (as^3 + bs^2 + cs + d)/(es^2 + fs + g)$$

$$a = (R_s + R_o) \cdot L_m$$

$$b = R_s R_m + R_s R_o + R_o R_m + L_m / C_o$$

$$c = R_s (C_m + C_o) / (C_m \cdot C_o) + R_m / C_o + R_o / C_m$$

$$d = 1 / C_m \cdot C_o$$

$$e = L_m$$

$$f = R_m + R_o$$

$$g = (C_m + C_o) / (C_m \cdot C_o)$$

$$k_t^2 = 1 - [(f_s/f_p)]^2$$

$$Q_s = 1 / \omega_s C_m (R_m + R_s)$$

$$Q_p = 1 / \omega_p C_m (R_m + R_o)$$

Step 2. Extraction Method of IDT Characteristics

Pitch (p): Distance between adjacent fingers of the IDT, crucial for determining f_s and kt^2 .

Number of Fingers: Affects the impedance and bandwidth.

Material Selection: Choose a piezoelectric material with appropriate cutting angle to optimize performance.

$$k_t^2 = 0.006162f_s^2 - 0.009447f_s + 0.5418$$

Step 3. Circuit Topology

mBVD Model Implementation: Use the modified Butterworth-Van Dyke model to represent the SAW resonator in the circuit.

Component Selection: Select capacitors, inductors, and resistors based on the extracted IDT parameters.

Fig1. Equivalent Circuit

Step 4. Elasticity Matrix Analysis:

Table 1. Elasticity Matrix Analysis

Sl. No.	Material	Elasticity Matrix Values [GPa]
1	Quartz (SiO ₂)	87.6, 7.04, 11.9, 7.04, 57.6, 11.9, 0, 0, 0, 7.04, 0, 11.9, 11.9, 0, 57.6, 0, 0, 0, 11.9, 0, 39.4
2	Lithium Niobate (LiNbO ₃)	203, 53, 75, 53, 57, 75, 0, 0, 0, 53, 0, 75, 75, 0, 57, 0, 0, 0, 75, 0, 69
3	Lithium Tantalate (LiTaO ₃)	231, 59, 76, 59, 64, 76, 0, 0, 0, 59, 0, 76, 76, 0, 64, 0, 0, 0, 76, 0, 70
4	Zinc Oxide (ZnO)	209.7, 121.1, 105.1, 121.1, 43.5, 105.1, 0, 0, 0, 121.1, 0, 105.1, 105.1, 0, 43.5, 0, 0, 0, 105.1, 0, 42.5
5	Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)	118, 53.8, 53.8, 53.8, 59.4, 53.8, 0, 0, 0, 53.8, 0, 53.8, 53.8, 0, 59.4, 0, 0, 0, 53.8, 0, 59.4
6	Aluminum Nitride (AlN)	345, 125, 120, 125, 120, 120, 0, 0, 0, 125, 0, 120, 120, 0, 120, 0, 0, 0, 120, 0, 122
7	Lanthanum Gallium Silicate (Langasite, La ₃ Ga ₅ SiO ₁₄)	151.3, 65.1, 66.3, 65.1, 49.2, 66.3, 0, 0, 0, 65.1, 0, 66.3, 66.3, 0, 49.2, 0, 0, 0, 66.3, 0, 60.5
8	Potassium Niobate (KNbO ₃)	167, 67, 68, 67, 66, 68, 0, 0, 0, 67, 0, 68, 68, 0, 66, 0, 0, 0, 68, 0, 94
9	Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT)	60, 24, 24, 24, 24, 24, 0, 0, 0, 24, 0, 24, 24, 0, 24, 0, 0, 0, 24, 0, 25
10	Gallium Nitride (GaN)	278, 118, 118, 118, 186, 118, 0, 0, 0, 118, 0, 118, 118, 0, 186, 0, 0, 0, 118, 0, 186

Fig2. Elastic Properties of Selected Materials

Understanding the electrical and mechanical interactions of piezoelectric materials through coupling matrix analysis is important for their use in sensors, actuators, and energy harvesting systems. The research is centered on various materials such as Quartz (SiO_2), Lithium Niobate (LiNbO_3), Lithium Tantalate (LiTaO_3), Zinc Oxide (ZnO), Gallium Arsenide (GaAs), Aluminum Nitride (AlN), Languasite ($\text{La}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{SiO}_{14}$), Potassium Niobate (KNbO_3), Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT), and Gallium Nitride (GaN). These substances display distinctive coupling properties, as shown in the coupling matrix, a key factor that describes how electrical fields and mechanical strains are interconnected. The coupling matrix of each material is graphed to analyze the variations in values among different indices, giving a deeper understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the materials when subjected to electrical and mechanical pressures. Examining the connection matrices exposes notable variances in the piezoelectric characteristics, allowing for customization of materials for precise purposes such as high-frequency devices, energy harvesting systems, or high-precision actuators. Engineers can enhance their choice and optimization of piezoelectric materials for various technological uses by comprehending their behavior. The graphs produced in this study provide a visual way to compare how the coupling values change among different materials, giving a clear view of how each material's inherent characteristics affect its overall performance.

Step 6. Relative Permittivity and Density Analysis:

Table 3. Relative Permittivity and Density Analysis

Sl. No.	Material	Relative Permittivity ϵ_r	Density ρ g/cm
1	Quartz (SiO_2)	4.65, 4.65, 4.6	2.65
2	Lithium Niobate (LiNbO_3)	43, 43, 28	4.65
3	Lithium Tantalate (LiTaO_3)	45, 45, 33	7.46
4	Zinc Oxide (ZnO)	8.75, 8.75, 7.8	5.67
5	Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)	12.9	5.32
6	Aluminum Nitride (AlN)	8.5, 8.5, 10.7	3.26
7	Lanthanum Gallium Silicate (Langasite, $\text{La}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{SiO}_{14}$)	13, 13, 13	6.72
8	Potassium Niobate (KNbO_3)	49, 49, 34	4.86
9	Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT)	1800, 1800, 2000	7.5
10	Gallium Nitride (GaN)	9.5	6.1

These values offer information on the material characteristics required to enhance the functionality of electronic, photonic, and piezoelectric systems. The wide range of ϵ_r and ρ in different materials makes it possible to customize properties for specific uses in the areas of sensors, actuators, and high-frequency electronics.

Step 7: Simulation

Simulation holds a crucial position in the development and enhancement of SAW resonators and the circuits they are connected to. By employing sophisticated simulation software like MATLAB and COMSOL Multiphysics, it is possible to accurately model and analyse the system's performance. Parameter sweeps are carried out to maximize important factors like pitch, number of fingers, and material properties to ensure the resonator meets performance requirements. Furthermore, the system's impedance and frequency response are simulated to confirm they align with theoretical predictions, allowing for a strong design process and improving the accuracy of the final implementation.

IV. RESULTS

Fig4. Elastic Plot

Fig5. Permittivity Plot

Fig6. Density Plot

Fig7. SAW Unit Resonator Geometry

Fig8. Deformation Plot

Fig9. Electric Plot

Considering the Rayleigh wave velocity of the material and the dimensions of the device as specified in the problem is crucial when estimating the resonant frequencies of SAW devices on different piezoelectric substrates. The basic SAW frequency (f_0) can be determined by the equation $f_0 = vR/\lambda$, with vR being the Rayleigh wave velocity of the substrate material and λ equal to the width of the geometry (4 μm).

Table 4. Rayleigh Wave Velocity and Fundamental Frequencies

Sl. No.	Material	Rayleigh wave velocity vR	f_0
1	Quartz (SiO ₂)	5960 m/s	1.49 GHz
2	Lithium Niobate (LiNbO ₃)	3488 m/s	872 MHz
3	Lithium Tantalate (LiTaO ₃)	3480m/s	870 MHz
4	Zinc Oxide (ZnO)	4170 m/s	1.04 GHz
5	Gallium Arsenide (GaAs)	3100m/s	775 MHz
6	Aluminum Nitride (AlN)	10800m/s	2.7 GHz
7	Lanthanum Gallium Silicate (Langasite, La ₃ Ga ₅ SiO ₁₄)	2950 m/s	737.5 MHz
8	Potassium Niobate (KNbO ₃)	3930 m/s	982.5 MHz
9	Lead Zirconate Titanate (PZT)	3800 m/s	950 MHz
10	Gallium Nitride (GaN)	5120 m/s	1.28 GHz

Fig10. Fundamental SAW Frequencies for Various Materials

These computations provide estimates of the basic SAW frequencies for each substrate, taking into account the specified geometry. Differences in specific material properties and device dimensions can lead to variations in actual resonant frequencies. The selection of the substrate is determined by the preferred operating frequency and specific application needs. AlN has a frequency of 2.7 GHz and is suitable for high-frequency applications, whereas Quartz has a frequency of 1.49 GHz, providing stability and making it ideal for standard SAW resonator designs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the resonant frequencies of Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW) devices fabricated on different piezoelectric substrates. The Rayleigh wave velocity (vR) and the device geometry (wavelength, $\lambda = 4\mu m$) were used to estimate the fundamental SAW frequency (f_0) for each material. The study results can be outlined as follows: Out of the ten materials examined, Aluminum Nitride (AlN) had the highest resonant frequency of 2.7 GHz, with Lanthanum Gallium Silicate (Langasite) having the lowest at 737.5 MHz. Substances like AlN, Quartz, and Zinc Oxide (ZnO) are more appropriate for high-frequency uses, whereas Langasite and Gallium Arsenide (GaAs) are well-suited for lower-frequency uses. Quartz, with a moderate frequency of 1.49 GHz and high stability, is suggested for accurate uses, whereas AlN's higher frequency makes it perfect for advanced high-frequency designs. When choosing substrate materials, take into account more than just the operating frequency and also consider factors like thermal stability, mechanical durability, and electrical performance. AlN and ZnO are recommended for high-frequency use because they have SAW frequencies of 2.7 GHz and 1.04 GHz, respectively, whereas Quartz is still the top choice for applications needing thermal and frequency stability. This evaluation

highlights the crucial importance of material selection in designing SAW resonators for a variety of applications, from telecommunications to precise sensing systems. Future efforts will emphasize validating these estimates through experiments and exploring more material properties to enhance SAW device performance.

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